

D2.7: Report on Stakeholder Workshop III

INFRAFRONTIER / IMPC Stakeholder Conference 2019: Genetic Variation, Big Data and Ageing

INFRAFRONTIER

IMPC

June 3rd – 5th 2019

Helsinki, Finland

Reported by:

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Summary

The INFRAFRONTIER / IMPC Stakeholder Conference 2019: Genetic Variation, Big Data and Ageing (3rd – 5th June 2019) was attended by 200 participants from more than 22 countries across Europe, East-Asia, North America and Australia, and was jointly organized with the International Mouse Phenotyping Consortium (IMPC) in Helsinki, Finland. Biocenter Oulu from University of Oulu was the co-organiser and national local host of the event. There was good gender balance among the participants (40% female) and invited speakers (50% males) and the event was extensively communicated via Tweeter during the conference and the week leading up to it.

The IPAD-MD project (GA. No. 653961) offered the opportunity for IPAD-MD partners and working groups to present their latest updates during four sessions (2A-C and 3) of the conference. In addition, working group breakout meetings on the last day of the conference were also supported by IPAD-MD. The involvement of the IMPC in this conference was made possible by IPAD-MD and it in turn facilitated cooperative efforts, discussions and strategic planning among INFRAFRONTIER partners, IMPC members and key international stakeholders.

Understanding the role of **human genetic variation and its functional analysis** is the next big step in genomic and precision medicine. The collection of such genomic data and its analysis falls into the category of **big data sciences** that has become commonplace in the present biomedical research landscape. In addition to this need, an increasing worldwide ageing population warrants the **better understanding of the ageing processes and diseases associated with ageing** to not only improve longevity but also to improve the quality of long life. These ideas were the basis for the **INFRAFRONTIER / IMPC Conference 2019**.

This conference provided an excellent opportunity to support a better alignment of INFRAFRONTIER / IMPC platforms with current ageing and big data initiatives along with

supporting interactions with human genetics centres and clinical consortia to promote the functional analysis of human genetic variation.

The Stakeholder Meeting was broadly divided into the following sessions:

1. Genomic big data from population isolates
2. IMPC: Emerging insights into genomic and precision medicine
3. Understanding genetic variation using IMPC big data
4. Model organisms in ageing research
5. Animal models for studying genetic variation
6. Stakeholder presentations

The **main objectives** of the conference were:

- To raise awareness of INFRAFRONTIER / IMPC platforms among the population genetics and ageing research community.
- To develop collaborative opportunities in advancing functional genetic variation and ageing research with model organisms.
- To present use cases for the utility of model organisms to study genetic variation in population isolates and decipher ageing mechanisms.
- To strengthen interactions with ageing and population genetics research consortia.
- To showcase emerging insights from IMPC towards understanding functional genetic variation and developing precision medicine.

Conference Venue: HANASAARI (HANAHOLMEN) - Swedish-Finnish Cultural Centre

The INFRAFRONTIER / IMPC Conference 2019 took place in the main lecture hall of the venue.

Agenda

MONDAY JUNE 3		Hanaholmen – Swedish-Finnish Cultural Centre	
	09:00 – 10:10	Introduction and Keynote	
	09:00 – 09:30	Welcome and Introduction Martin Hrabě de Angelis, <i>INFRAFRONTIER, Helmholtz Center Munich</i> Riina Vuorento, <i>Ministry of Education and Culture, Finland</i> Riitta Maijala, <i>Academy of Finland</i> Marja Makarow, <i>Biocenter Finland</i>	
KEYNOTE	09:30 – 10:10	Taina Pihlajaniemi, <i>University of Oulu</i> The Great Power and Versatility of Mouse Models in Understanding MACIT and Multiplexin Collagens in Cell-Extracellular Matrix Interplay	
	10:10 – 10:30	COFFEE BREAK	
SESSION 1	10:30 – 12:30	Genomic Big Data from Population Isolates Chair: Johanna Myllyharju, <i>University of Oulu</i>	
 INFRAFRONTIER	10:30 – 10:35	Intro by Session Chair	
KEYNOTE	10:35 – 11:15	Aarno Palotie, <i>Institute of Molecular Medicine Finland (FIMM)</i> Finnish Disease Heritage and FinnGen	
	11:15 – 11:40	Guðrið Andorsdóttir Ellefsen, <i>The Genetic Biobank of the Faroe Islands</i> FarGen: Genetics, longevity and public health within the Faroese population	
	11:40 – 12:05	Hardip Patel, <i>National Centre for Indigenous Genomics</i> Australia's National Centre for Indigenous Genomics ensuring the inclusion of Indigenous Australians in Precision Medicine	
	12:05 – 12:30	Terry-Lynn Young, <i>Memorial University of Newfoundland</i> The Newfoundland Curse	

MONDAY JUNE 3

12:30 – 13:30

LUNCH

SESSION 2A 13:30 – 15:00

13:30 – 14:00

Emerging Insights into Genomic and Precision Medicine

Chair: [Steve Brown](#), *IMPC*, *MRC Harwell*

Introduction to IMPC

- IMPC: brief summary update [Steve Brown](#), *IMPC*
- International Mouse Phenotyping Consortium – Preparing for Horizon Europe and Beyond [Kalliopoi Kostelidou](#), *IMPC*

14:00 – 15:00

Age-related Phenotyping in IMPC

- Progress (update on numbers), logistics, SOPs [Sara Wells](#), *MRC Harwell*
- DCC and data loading (what is displayed on the portal etc. Remaining tasks) [Piia Keskivali-Bond](#), *MRC Harwell*
- Data analysis tools and initial data analysis [MPI2](#)
- Additional tests and frailty index [Antonio Aguilar-Pimentel](#), *Helmholtz Center Munich*
- Pilot tests in the intervening periods [Silvia Mandillo](#), *CNR*, [Jan Prochazka](#), *IMG*, [Sara Wells](#), *MRC Harwell*

15:00 – 15:15

COFFEE BREAK

SESSION 2B 15:15 – 17:40

15:15 – 15:40

Emerging Insights into Genomic and Precision Medicine

Chair: [Mary Dickinson](#), *Baylor College of Medicine*

Immunophenotyping

- Implementation of immunophenotyping data analysis workflow and resulting biological insights [John Seavitt](#), *Baylor College*, [Lauryl Nutter](#), *TCP*
- EmbedSOM, a self-organizing map-based software tool for multi-dimensional cytometry data analysis [Vendula Novosadova](#), *IMG*

15:40 – 16:05

Behaviour and Sensory

- Emerging insights from neurobehavioural pipeline: paper conclusions
[Michelle Stewart](#), [MRC Harwell](#), [Ann Flenniken](#), [TCP](#),
[Elissa Chesler](#), [Jackson Laboratory](#)
- New phenotyping developments: Gait analysis, Adhesive removal test, Home cage analysis and ultrasonic vocalisations
[Michelle Stewart](#), [MRC Harwell](#), [Silvia Mandillo](#), [CNR](#)

16:05 – 16:35

Cardiovascular and Metabolism

- Update on the IMPC Cardio Paper: New Biological Insights from Cardio Screen
[Nadine Spielmann](#), [Helmholtz Center Munich](#)
- Interplay between embryonic and adult phenotypes
[Mary Dickinson](#), [Baylor College](#), [Lydia Teboul](#), [MRC Harwell](#),
[Henrik Westerberg](#), [MRC Harwell](#)

16:35 – 17:05

Embryo Phenotyping

- MicroCT imaging of early embryos in embryonic lethal pipeline
[Michaela Prochazkova](#), [IMG](#)
- Embryo Analysis Update [Henrik Westerberg](#), [MRC Harwell](#)
- Subviable Analysis Update [Hugh Morgan](#), [MRC Harwell](#)

17:05 - 17:40

Morphology

- X-ray test annotation – Reference atlas update [Jesús Ruberte, UAB](#)
- Eye Morphology test annotation – Zegami online image library for baseline and mutant annotation training and jamborees [Colin McKerlie, TCP](#)
- High-throughput in-vivo microCT in skeleton morphology phenotyping [Jan Prochazka, IMG](#)
- Gross Pathology test and Tissue Embedding test Enquiry function at IMPC portal – Implementation [Alba Gómez, EMBL-EMI](#)
- Histopathology test – Completing required annotation gaps in uploaded data, Displaying hits at the Portal, Preliminary LAP histopathology update [Colin McKerlie, TCP](#)

18:15

BUS DEPARTURE TO RESTAURANT

19:00

SOCIAL DINNER FOR ALL PARTICIPANTS

SESSION 2C 08:15 – 09:45

Emerging Insights into Genomic and Precision MedicineChair: [Colin McKerlie](#), *TCP*

08:15 – 08:45

Molecular Phenotyping

- General Summary [Kent Lloyd](#), *UC Davis*
- Metabolomics [Kent Lloyd](#), *UC Davis*
- Developments in the analysis of the microbiome [Kent Lloyd](#), *UC Davis*
- Proteomics [David Schibli](#), *UVic*
- Epigenomics [Archana Tomar](#), *Helmholtz Center Munich*
- PCDDP progress update [Anne Grobler](#), *PCDDP*

08:45 – 09:45

Nociception

- Overview and outline of the hour session [Jacqui White](#), *Jackson Laboratory*
- Formalin [Jacqui White](#), *Jackson Laboratory*
- CFA – von Frey, Hargreaves', Edema [Ann Flenniken](#), *TCP*
- Adaptations for HTP compatibility: CFA - Cage Lid Interaction, and Dynamic Weight Bearing [Rob Bonin](#), *University of Toronto*
- Unchallenged strategies [Michelle Stewart](#), *MRC Harwell*
- Landing page [Daniel Delbarre](#), *MRC Harwell*
- Summary recommendations, Publication Plans, Acknowledgements & Questions [Jacqui White](#), *Jackson Laboratory*

09:45 – 10:05

COFFEE BREAK

SESSION 3 10:05 – 11:50

Understanding Genetic Variation using IMPC Big Data

Chair: [Ann-Marie Mallon](#), *MRC Harwell*

10:10 – 11:50

MPI2: Informatics and Big Data

- New website and comms [Terry Meehan](#), *EMBL-EBI*, [Kieran Gibson](#), *IMPC*
- Tracking precision medicine models [Alba Gómez](#), *EMBL-EBI*
- Data capture, standardisation and QC of phenotyping data [Luis Santos](#), *MRC Harwell*
- MPI2 Manuscript updates [Violeta Munoz Fuentes](#), *EMBL-EBI*
- Phenopackets and Statpackets [Jeremy Mason](#), *EMBL-EBI*
- Novel Disease Gene Discovery in the 100K Genomes using mouse data [Valentina Cipriani](#), *QMUL*
- Improvements to integration and comparative analysis of mouse and human large-scale datasets [Tomasz Konopka](#), *QMUL*
- RRIDS [Anita Bandrowski](#), *UC San Diego*

KEYNOTE 11:50 – 12:30

Translational insights to vascular growth factors

[Kari Alitalo](#), *University of Helsinki*

12:30 – 13:30

LUNCH

SESSION 4 13:30 – 17:30

INFRAFRONTIER 13:30 – 13:35

Model Organisms in Ageing Research

Chair: [Valérie Gailus-Durner](#), *Helmholtz Center Munich*

Intro by Session Chair

13:35 – 14:00

[Brun Ulfhake](#), *Karolinska Institutet*

Behavioural assessment of ageing and its dependence on the integrity of sensory mechanisms

TUESDAY JUNE 4

14:00 – 14:25 **Mart Saarma, *University of Helsinki***
Development of growth factor therapies for Parkinson's disease

14:25 – 14:50 **Peppi Karppinen, *University of Oulu***
Systemic long-term inactivation of hypoxia-inducible factor prolyl 4-hydroxylase 2 ameliorates aging-induced changes in mice without affecting the life span

14:50 – 15:50 POSTER SESSION AND COFFEE BREAK

15:50 – 16:15 **Bruno Reversade, *A*Star Institute, Singapore***
Solved and unsolved premature ageing syndromes and our use of animal and patient-derived organoids for disease modeling

16:15 – 16:40 **Dan Ehninger, *German Center for Neurodegenerative Diseases***
Lifespan and healthspan in mice: mechanisms and interventions

16:40 – 17:05 **Celia Martinez-Jimenez, *Helmholtz Center Munich***
Effect of ageing on cellular variability and transcriptional dynamics

17:05 – 17:30 **Fabio Mammano, *CNR***
An INFRAFRONTIER mouse model of partial connexin 26 deficiency provides critical insight into the etiopathogenesis of age-related hearing loss

**17:30 – 20:00 SOCIAL EVENT:
BOAT TRIP ACROSS THE HELSINKI ARCHIPELAGO**

SESSION 5

09:00 – 10:20

INFRAFRONTIER

09:00 – 09:05

Animal Models for Studying Genetic VariationChair: Jukka Kallijärvi, *University of Helsinki*

Intro by Session Chair

09:05 – 09:30

Hannes Lohi, *University of Helsinki*

Canine models of human disease

09:30 – 09:55

Anu Suomalainen-Wartiovaara, *University of Helsinki*

Mechanisms for mitochondrial disorders using genetically tailored disease models

09:55 – 10:20

Fuad Iraqi, *University of Tel Aviv*

Collaborative Cross mice offer the greatest genetic diversity resource population for studying complex diseases and modifiers for IMPC project

10:20 – 10:40

COFFEE BREAK

SESSION 6

10:40 – 12:20

INFRAFRONTIER

10:40 – 11:00

Stakeholder PresentationsChair: Michael Raess, *INFRAFRONTIER***Daniel Rhodes**, *Queen Mary University of London (QMUL)*

Constraint and phenotypic similarity characterization of drug targets and their paralogs to inform on drug side effects

11:00 – 11:20

Eleonora Leucci, *KU Leuven, LifeTime*

PDX as relevant preclinical models: Trace experience

WEDNESDAY JUNE 5

11:20 – 11:40	Satu Kuure, <i>University of Helsinki</i> Omics profiling as a tool to identify metabolic profiles of kidney progenitors
11:40 – 12:00	Jukka Kallijärvi, <i>University of Helsinki</i> A spontaneous mitonuclear epistasis converging on Rieske Fe-S protein exacerbates complex III deficiency in mice
12:00 – 12:20	Pasi Kankaanpää, <i>Euro-Biolmaging</i> Euro-Biolmaging can complement INFRAFRONTIER/IMPC services in life sciences
12:20 – 12:30	Wrap Up and Closing Remarks Michael Raess, <i>INFRAFRONTIER</i>
12:30 – 13:30	LUNCH

Scope and Context

The INFRAFRONTIER / IMPC Conference 2019 built on the success of the IPAD-MD Workshop on Global Access to Common Resources (INFRAFRONTIER / IMPC Stakeholder Meeting 2017) in Athens in November 2017 (MS4) and the IPAD-MD Stakeholder Workshop ‘Focus on Innovation’ (INFRAFRONTIER / IMPC Stakeholder Meeting 2018) in Munich in December 2018 (MS5). This INFRAFRONTIER / IMPC Conference 2019 is focussed on three main topics: genetic variation, big data and ageing.

Understanding the role of **human genetic variation and its functional consequences** is the next big step in precision medicine. Information on human disease-associated coding variants is available from single case studies, robust genome wide association studies and population genetic screens. Genetic studies on isolated founder populations are a rich source of novel pathogenic variants and new genotype-phenotype associations. However, these association studies do not always confirm causation. An effective way to acquire information about the mechanisms leading to diseases is to replicate genetic changes in appropriate model systems and functionally analysing any resulting phenotypic changes. There is a concerted

effort among INFRAFRONTIER partners and IMPC members to accomplish this by designing and producing a genome-wide mouse strain resource of human disease-associated coding variants that can be used for validation of putative pathological variants and provide valuable insight into the disease mechanism.

Recent advances in biomedical technologies like whole exome and genome sequencing, genome-editing and state of the art multi-faceted phenotyping has led to generation of large amounts of valuable data ushering in the era of '**big data genomics**'. These data sets contain a wealth of valuable information that can be combined and complemented to other larger data sets. The genomic and phenotypic data from IMPC and INFRAFRONTIER databases represent a treasure trove of biological information that can be exploited to push the boundaries of fundamental and translational biomedical research. Thus, it is high time to carefully present, collect, analyse and interpret these enormous data sets, as the first steps utilising these recent advances.

The last century has witnessed an ever-increasing ageing population worldwide owing to the improvement in general public health. This has, however, also increased the incidences of late-onset diseases and ageing related co-morbidities resulting in longer but unhealthy lives. This warrants the better understanding of the **ageing processes and ageing-related diseases** to not only increase longevity but also to improve the quality of long life. Ageing research employing animal models offers promising way to understand the genetics behind ageing and age-related disorders as well as to uncover evolutionary conserved ageing mechanisms amenable to therapeutic intervention.

To contribute to these pressing issues, INFRAFRONTIER together with IMPC and Biocenter Oulu organised this **INFRAFRONTIER / IMPC Conference 2019**. The conference involves world-leading experts in functional genetic variation, population genetics and ageing, offers an excellent opportunity for aligning INFRAFRONTIER / IMPC platforms with current frontline research of these selected topics and provides a platform for fruitful interactions between mouse geneticists, population geneticists and ageing experts.

Meeting Overview

Day 1 (03.06.19)

Welcome / Introduction talks and Session 1: Genomic Big Data from Population Isolates

Prof. Dr. Martin Hrabě de Angelis started off the conference with a welcome talk that included a brief introduction of INFRAFRONTIER, IMPC and the goals of the conference. Riina Vuorento from the Finnish Ministry of Education and Culture welcomed all the participants and highlighted the importance of data generation, storage and access in and between distributed European infrastructures. Dr. Riitta Maijala (Vice President for Research, Academy of Finland) briefly introduced the Finnish Research Infrastructure (FIRI) funding scheme, its key principles of action and Finland's strategy and roadmap for RIs 2014 - 2020. Next was a snapshot of Biocenter Finland, nationwide research-infrastructure network, given by its Director Dr. Marja Makarow.

The first keynote lecture was given by Prof. Dr. Taina Pihlajaniemi, a pioneer at the forefront of extracellular matrix (ECM) and collagen research. Prof. Pihlajaniemi showcased the importance of mouse models in understanding the interplay between membrane-associated collagens with interrupted triple-helices (MACITs) and multiplex collagens in the ECM and expertly described their mechanisms and significance in development and tumorigenesis.

Session 1: Genomic Big Data from Population Isolates started with another informative keynote lecture by Prof. Dr. Aarno Palotie about the Finnish Disease Heritage and FinnGen. FinnGen is a large public-private partnership aiming to collect and analyse genome and health data from 500,000 Finns by the year 2023. In the first year and a half, by utilising the samples collected by a nationwide network of biobanks, FinnGen has delivered genotype and health data from 142,000 Finns and started a collaborative project to study genetic impacts on health over time. The study is based on combining genome information with digital health care data from national health registries. Prof. Palotie also presented enriched Finnish variants in

common diseases like type 2 diabetes, asthma, inflammatory bowel disease, various cancers as well as high impact variants. This segued into another population genome project from the Faroe Islands called FarGen presented by Dr. Ellefsen. FarGen is coordinated by the Genetic Biobank of the Faroe Islands and at present 2000 individuals have signed up with 1532 blood samples collected. The data from these samples is used to perform linkage studies among families and search for large chromosomal regions that segregate to affected individuals more often than would be expected by chance - an effective approach for finding rare variants with large effect (high penetrance). Session 1 was concluded by Dr. Hardip Patel from the National Centre for Indigenous Genomics, Australia who presented strong arguments for the use of diversity inclusive reference data for human genomics research and clinical use, and the need for standards in human genomic analysis to achieve interoperable data. Dr. Young was not able to attend the conference due to health issues.

Session 2: IMPC – Emerging Insights into Genomic and Precision Medicine

Session 2 was assigned for the IMPC and was split into three parts. Session 2A started with an introductory talk by Prof. Dr. Steve Brown that summarised the status quo and future plans for the IMPC. Dr. Kalliopoi Kostelidou, the new Program Manager for the IMPC briefly introduced herself and IMPC's preparation for Horizon Europe. The rest of the session 2A and 2B showcased the progress, updates and impactful results from the various IMPC working groups that included age-related phenotyping, immunophenotyping, behaviour, cardiovascular and metabolism, embryo phenotyping and morphology.

Day 2 (04.06.19)

IMPC Sessions 2C and 3, Session 4: Model Organisms in Ageing Research and Poster Session

The IMPC session on insights into genomic and precision medicine continued in to the second day with talks from the molecular phenotyping working group that included metabolomics

and microbiome analysis, and nociception working group that included topics on cage lid interaction, dynamic weight bearing and publication plans. Session 3 was also dedicated to the IMPC and dealt with using the enormous data generated by the consortium in understanding the consequence of genetic variation on health and disease. This session was spearheaded by the MPI2 and informatics working group with talks on tracking precision medicine models, data capture, standardization and QC of phenotyping data, and novel disease gene discovery in the 100k genomes using mouse data.

The third keynote by Prof. Alitalo on translational insights to vascular growth factors was scheduled between sessions 3 and 4. Prof. Alitalo presented examples of the translational therapeutic potential of vascular endothelial growth factors and angiopoietins. He also recapitulated the recent groundbreaking discovery of meningeal lymphatic vessels by his group, whose members attended the conference to facilitate further collaboration with INFRARONTIER. Prof. Alitalo ended his talk by underscoring the therapeutic potential of lymphangiogenic growth factors and their inhibitors in treating neurodegenerative and neuroinflammatory diseases.

Session 4 was focussed on model organisms in ageing research and was the longest session with 7 external invited speakers. The session comprised of diverse topics ranging from the development of growth factor therapies for Parkinson's (Prof. Saarma) to the use of home-cage monitoring to refine behavioural characterization of aging in mice (Prof. Ulfhake) and how ageing phenotypes unfold across the lifespan of mice and humans (Dr. Ehninger). The talks also showcased the use of state-of-the-art biomedical technologies like single cell sequencing to investigate if cell-to-cell gene expression variability increases during ageing on a genome-wide level (Dr. Martinez-Jimenez), and animal and patient-derived organoids for modelling premature ageing syndromes (Dr. Reversade). The Poster Session took place in the middle of session 4 with 23 posters selected from submitted abstracts.

Day 3 (05.06.19)

Session 5 and Stakeholder Presentations

The final day of the conference started with session 5 that focused on studying genetic variation using animal models. Research projects utilising mouse models to study the mechanisms for mitochondrial disorders (Prof. Suomalainen) and complex multi-focal diseases (Prof. Iraqi) were presented. Prof. Lohi from the University of Helsinki talked about their recent data on mapping several new loci and genes associated with neurological, neurodegenerative and neurobehavioral disorders like epilepsy, ataxia and anxiety in dogs by studying their impressive collection of 80 000 DNA samples from 330 different breeds. Prof. Lohi showcased how domestic dogs can be used as a tool to identify novel genes also behind human complex diseases.

The last session of the conference consisted of 5 stakeholder presentations that were selected from submitted abstracts. Dr. Rhodes from Queen Mary University of London described his work to systematically identify the association between the number of paralogs of a target protein and the number of side effects that involved curation of 2,806 high confidence sets of paralogs, protein sequence functional characterisation, amino acid sequence similarity and network-based community detection algorithms. This work was utilised advanced bioinformatics resources to improve drug development processes and success of clinical trials. Prof. Leucci represented EU's LifeTime consortium and presented patient-derived tumor xenograft (PDX) models as important preclinical models as well as the EurOPDX consortium and Trace - KU Leuven's PDX platform. The remaining talks focused on omics profiling to identify metabolic profiles of kidney progenitors (Dr. Kuure), a spontaneous mtDNA variant that exacerbated the manifestations caused by respiratory chain complex III deficiency in mice (Dr. Kallijärvi) and complementary Euro-BioImaging services for INFRAFRONTIER / IMPC members (Dr. Kankaanpää).

Main Outcomes of the Conference:

The conference was successful in underscoring the importance of genomic big data, genetic variation and ageing research to the INFRAFRONTIER consortium and IMPC members as well as to the wider medical research community. The conference also brought together population genetic researchers and the mouse researcher community and led to the exploration of several potential collaborations and new avenues of research.

The main outcomes of the conference were:

- Showcasing two population genetics projects, FarGen and FinnGen, to the mouse research community and highlighting the importance of biobanking in identifying novel human disease loci.
- Presenting IMPC's contribution to genomic medicine with scientifically relevant and diverse research contributions from the different working groups along with upcoming publication plans.
- Opportunities for discussing the future of IMPC and its focus on the study of functional genetic variation.
- Introducing INFRAFRONTIER / IMPC platforms to the population genetics research community.
- Setting up the stage for potential collaborations that include:
 - INFRAFRONTIER / IMPC members and the above-mentioned genomics project. For example, mouse knockout phenotypes that contribute to identification of genes contributing to human traits that are examined by FinnGenn.
 - Integration of dog and mouse phenotypic data could lead to new insights into human disease mechanisms.
 - Euro-BioImaging and IMPC to explore setting up collaborative analysis and setting up long-term sustainability of IMPC image data.